

Effect of green manure (GM) and Fe application on the Fe held by organic matter in redried submerged soils

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We investigated the effect of GM and Fe application on the Fe held by the organic matter in redried soils that varied in CaCO₃ content. The pot culture experiment was conducted on highly calcareous (pH 8.7, 0.56% organic C, 4.7% CaCO₃, and Fe held by organic matter at 25.3 mg/kg) and slightly calcareous (pH 8.5, 0.17% organic C, 0.25% CaCO₃, and Fe held by organic matter at 62.2 mg/kg) soils (Aeric Fluvaquent). pH was measured in a 1:2 soil:water suspension.

Two levels of dry green manure (0 and 1%) from *Sesbania aculeata* (total Fe content 307 mg/kg) and 4 Fe levels (0, 15, 30, and 60 mg/kg) from FeSO₄·7H₂O were used. Soils were submerged 85 and 145 d, then dried 30 d.

To determine Fe held by organic matter, dried soil was allowed to react overnight with 30% H₂O₂ (1:1 soil H₂O₂ ratio). The soil tubes were immersed in a beaker containing water maintained at 75°C + 2°C for completion of the reaction. Fe was

extracted with DTPA (1:4 soil DTPA ratio). To calculate Fe held by organic matter, a blank reading (without H₂O₂) was abstracted.

Submerging soil for 85 d increased the Fe held by organic matter from 25.3 to 28.9 mg/kg for highly calcareous soil and from 62.2 to 79.8 mg/kg for slightly calcareous soils (see table). Fe content further increased to 30.2 and 90.0 mg/kg after 145 d of submergence. The effect of submergence was more pronounced on slightly calcareous soil.

GM increased organic bound Fe significantly in both soils in both submergence periods. The effect was higher at 85 d in slightly calcareous soil; in highly calcareous soil, the effect was almost the same for both submergence intervals.

Adding Fe increased organic bound Fe significantly in both soils at both submergence intervals.

The interaction between GM and added Fe was significant only at 85 d of submergence in both the soils. □

Effect of GM and Fe application on Fe held by organic matter in soils redried after being submerged. Ludhiana, Punjab, India.

Fe applied (mg/kg)	Fe held by organic matter (mg/kg)					
	Submerged 85 d			Submerged 145 d		
	No GM	GM	Mean	No GM	GM	Mean
	Highly calcareous soil					
0	28.9	35.1	32.0	30.2	36.3	33.2
15	30.9	37.0	33.9	31.8	37.3	34.5
30	33.3	37.9	35.6	33.4	39.1	36.3
60	35.8	39.7	37.7	34.2	41.7	37.9
Mean	32.2	37.4		32.4	38.6	
	Slightly calcareous soil					
0	79.8	91.7	85.8	90.0	91.8	90.9
15	83.0	97.0	90.0	92.9	94.2	93.5
30	85.2	101.8	93.5	94.5	96.8	97.7
60	88.6	103.6	96.1	97.1	98.8	97.9
Mean	84.2	98.5		93.6	95.4	
CD (0.05)Fe		GM	Fe × GM	Fe	GM	Fe × GM
Calcareous	0.5	0.4	0.7	1.0	0.7	ns
Noncalcareous	0.6	0.5	0.9	0.8	0.5	ns

Estimating azolla cover

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Quantitative estimates of azolla cover during multiplication are important in assessing its agronomic applications and weed-suppressing properties. The faster covering occurs, the greater its weed suppression efficiency. When studying large areas in farmers' fields, it is useful to have a simple but precise method that is faster than the usual fresh and dry weight measurement.

A new scoring method, based on the Braun Blanquet Cover-Abundance

Scale, is proposed. The Braun Blanquet method is used by ecologists all over the world. In the table, the new scale is compared to the IRRI

scale used in azolla INSFFER trials.

The new scale is more precise: it gives, within the significant range of cover, lower and upper limits. Errors

Two scoring methods for estimating azolla cover.

IRRI method	Modified Braun Blanquet method
0 = no azolla	r = rare with small cover
2 = 25% azolla cover	+ = few, with small cover
4 = 50% azolla cover	1 = numerous but less than 1/20 cover (<5%)
6 = 75% azolla cover	2 = cover between 1/20 and 1/4 (6-25%)
8 = 100% azolla cover	3 = cover between 1/4 and 1/2 (26-50%)
10 = 100% azolla cover with overlapping growth	4 = cover between 1/2 and 3/4 (51-75%)
	5 = cover more than 3/4 (>75%)
	6 = cover more than 3/4 (>75%) with overlapping growth of azolla

can only occur in borderline cases. It should eventually improve data processing and interpretation.

To apply this method, estimate the

exact area of the plot and then the area of azolla cover. First ask: "Does azolla cover more or less than 50% of the area?" Continue to estimate

according to the scale. The same scale (except for level 6) can be used to estimate area covered by rice and by different weed species. □

Urea timing and application method in direct-seeded lowland rice

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A trial tested time and method of applying urea N on waterlogged (up to 50 cm submergence) direct-seeded rice during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons under rainfed conditions. OR117-8 (160 d) seed was broadcast on sandy clay loam (pH 5.1, 0.045% total N, 7 kg Olsen P/ha, and 50 kg K/ha). At sowing, 11 kg P/ha and 21 kg K/ha were applied uniformly. N as urea was applied at 50 kg/ha (see table).

Cured urea was prepared by mixing prilled urea 1:5 with moist soil and incubating 48 h in the shade. The rate of cured urea N was based on N added to the moist soil. When sufficient

Effect of urea and cured urea on grain yield of rice, Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)		
	1984	1985	Mean
Control (no N)	3.3	2.6	2.9
100% N at seeding as PU	4.0	4.1	4.0
100% N at seeding as CU	4.3	3.7	4.0
50% N as PU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	4.0	3.6	3.8
50% N as CU at seeding + 50% N as PU through spray	3.9	3.2	3.5
50% N as PU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at panicle initiation (PI)	4.4	3.7	4.0
50% N as CU at seeding + 25% at 30 DAS + 25% at PI	4.1	3.6	3.8
50% N as PU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	5.0	4.5	4.1
50% N at CU at 40 DAS + 25% at 61 DAS + 25% at PI	4.4	3.1	4.0
CD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	—

^a PU = prilled urea, CU = cured urea.

rainwater became available, the seedbed was plowed down by a wooden country plow followed by planking (a common practice in Orissa) at 30 d after sowing (DAS). Weeding and gapfilling were done at 40 DAS.

Application of 50% N at 40 DAS plus 25% at 61 DAS and 25% at panicle initiation gave the highest grain yield in both years. Applying 100% N as urea at seeding gave consistently good yields. Cured urea proved to be inferior to prilled urea. □

An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions

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Analysis of a soil solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for soil chemical environment analyses. However, it is difficult to obtain a sample from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC potted soils with different densities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried

(>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing solution was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacement solution. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement fluid appeared in the first 200 ml.

About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils with fast drainage properties.

In a second experiment, we compared soil solution collected by the displacement method with equilibrated saturation extracts of three soils. Equilibrium was ensured by recycling the saturation extracts three times. Saturating a soil to FC, then immediately draining it does not give equilibrium extract. Allowing FC soils to remain saturated for a long time (beyond 8 h in many cases) might cause soil reduction.

We used three soils set up as in the first experiment, replicated six times. Demineralized water, in volumes required to bring the FC soils to saturation, was poured on the soil surface. The first 125-ml leachates